

D9.2: Risk Management plan v.1.0

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3.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	NO
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5.	Partner	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	NTNU	NO
6.	Partner	UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN	ULEI	NL
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Revision history:

This is the first version of the Risk Management Plan (RMP) of XR4Human. The RMP will be updated when necessary.

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	24.01.2023	Rigmor C. Baraas (USN)	Preparation of the first draft
0.2	07.03.2023	Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA)	Review of the first draft
0.3	07.03.2023	Rigmor C. Baraas (USN)	Preparation of the second draft
0.4	19.04.2023	Mary Anderson-Glenna (USN)	Review of the second draft
1.0	27.04.2023	Rosemarie DLC Bernabe (USN/UiO) and Rigmor C. Baraas (USN)	Final version

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1 XR4Human Management Structure and Procedures

Risks are probabilities of harm or unwanted consequences. The management of risks is integral to XR4Human's management structure, which functions as follows.

1.1 Management Structure of XR4Human

The purpose of project management is to ensure the proper level of co-ordination and cooperation amongst the consortium members and to timely report to the EC.

Additionally, project management has the following responsibilities: project administration, project organization, management of the scientific progress of the project, coordination with other EC-funded projects and other interested parties and coordinating effective dissemination and communication of the project results. The partners involved have agreed on developing an effective and decentralized management structure based on delegated responsibilities. XR4Human's project management system will provide full transparency and control of the entire project in terms of time, resources, and cost tracking.

Project operation will involve the following roles or groups:

- The Coordinators
- General Assembly (GA)
- Executive Board (EB)
- Work Package Leaders (WPLs)
- Task Leaders
- External Advisory Board (EAB)

The mandate and the scope of these roles and groups are described below. Their role in risk management is also identified.

The decision-making authority has been divided between the General Assembly and the Executive Board to ensure open and fair decision-making, while allowing for agile project management and time-efficient monitoring of the progress. The Executive Board will assist the Coordinators and the General Assembly in order to reduce the administrative workload of work package leaders, as they are also key scientists in the project.

The coordinators and the support team

The coordinators and the support team at USN (coordinating entity) are the link between the project partners and the European Commission. They will be responsible for the proper performance of the tasks as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. In particular, the coordinators will be responsible for:

- Providing any document or information required by the EC
- Timely submission of deliverables and periodic and final reports to the EC
- Managing the payments to the members of the Consortium
- Summoning, organizing, and chairing the EB meetings
- Organizing the yearly GA meetings and summoning the GA, Executive Board and External Advisory Board
- Ensuring that the governing documents and other important project internal information are available on the project Sharepoint

The support team will support in administrative and financial tasks.

The General Assembly (GA)

Role: The GA is the supreme decision-making body of XR4Human and is responsible for the major strategic and scientific decisions. The GA has one representative from each of the project partners. It is chaired by the Coordinators. The GA will monitor the status regarding the scientific progress, costs, quality, and

communication and compare the current and planned status. The GA will convene at the annual project meeting to revise and update the plans for the upcoming year. Further, the GA will monitor the knowledge gained, the list of stakeholders, and the project risks. If needed, updates will be made, and actions will be taken regarding these issues. In particular, the GA will be responsible for the issues listed below.

- Review the scientific progress and costs incurred so far
- Re-distribute tasks and/or budget within the consortium, if necessary
- Decide whether requests for contract amendments are to be made, if necessary
- Adopt a scientific work plan for the upcoming year
- Review the dissemination and communication activities, compare to the plan, and adopt a dissemination/communication plan for the upcoming year
- Review the quality of the work and results so far, applying the quality management plan
- Review the project risks and adopt an updated risk response plan based on the project so far and identification of potentially emerging new risks
- Review the data and knowledge gained so far and decide actions according to the data, innovation, and IP/knowledge management plans on e.g., data storage and exploitation of results
- Resolve conflicts related to the project activities, if these can't be resolved at a lower level (i.e., WP level, Task level)
- Decide on changes in the Consortium Agreement, if necessary
- Meetings: The GA will convene physically at the beginning of the project and then, once a year. Notice of the upcoming meeting will be given 30 calendar days prior to the meeting and the agenda will be distributed 21 days prior to the meeting. In cases of substantive changes of the project (e.g., partner termination, request for project extension) the coordinator can plan a special/extraordinary GA, if necessary.
- Voting rights and quorum in the GA: The GA's decision is binding and valid if a quorum is reached, i.e., 2/3 of the members are present. If a quorum is not reached, the chairpersons shall arrange an online meeting for the purposes of reaching a quorum within 15 calendar days. Each member of the GA has one vote. In the case of a tie poll, the Coordinators will have two votes.

The Executive Board (EB)

Role: The EB consists of the Coordinators and Work Package Leaders. The coordinator is the chair of the EB. The EB oversees the day-to-day management of XR4Human's project activities, in particular:

- Track and monitor the progress of the WP activities.
- Monitor potential deviations from the work plans and reporting them to the GA.
- Manage the data and IP/knowledge gained in the project, the innovation, quality, and risks according to their respective management plans.
- Initiate mitigating actions, in line with the risk response plan.
- Ensure sufficient communication between the WPs to obtain seamless interfaces between them.
- Facilitate resolution of conflicts.

Meetings: The EB will meet every month. If necessary, the Coordinators can call additional EB virtual meetings.

Decision-making: The EB has the authority to make decisions on the daily activities of XR4HUMAN to ensure that the yearly plans for science, dissemination, and communication are fulfilled. Further, the EB has the authority to initiate actions needed to execute the knowledge, quality, and risk management plans.

The Work Package Leaders (WPLs)

Role: The WPLs are responsible for the daily progress of the WP activities. The WPLs manage the work within the WP assigned to them in accordance with the Grant Agreement (GA) and the yearly plans adopted by the GA. The WPLs will in particular:

- Take actions to ensure satisfactory progress of the WP activities
- Initiate meetings within the WP when needed
- Initiate meetings between WPs when needed
- Participate in the EB

Meetings: The WPLs will meet monthly. Frequent communication is important to ensure that the WPs are well aligned with well-established communication routes and that inputs and outputs arrive in time, and it is particularly important at the beginning of the project.

The External Advisory Board (EAB)

Role: The EAB will provide input to the scientific dissemination/communication and risk response plans for the upcoming year and comment on the quality of the project. The EAB will advise on strategic decisions within the project. Members of the EAB will review selected project deliverables. A member of the EAB with relevant expertise will hold the role of the XR4HUMAN Ethics Advisor, with responsibility for highlighting ethical aspects of the project.

2 Risk Management Procedures

2.1 Risk Identification

The following risks were identified in the proposal stage:

Description of risk
Coordinator leaves coordinating institution
Partner becomes unable to conduct allocated tasks
In person meetings / stakeholder engagement / data collection becomes impossible in some countries

As new risks are identified in the EB meetings, they will be added to the project risk log (PM² Risk Log) where related risk management actions will be detailed. Risks will be updated in the continuous reporting module in SyGMA.

2.2 Addressing and Mitigating Risks

The following risk-mitigation measures will be observed for the risks identified during the preparation of the proposal:

Description of Risk	Proposed Risk-Mitigation Measures
Coordinator leaves coordinating institution	Coordinating institution appoints new coordinator – Several experienced project leaders already involved in the project could take the role effectively
Partner becomes unable to conduct allocated tasks	The preferred measure is to re-allocate the tasks between existing members in the consortium. If this is not possible the task will be sub-contracted to a suitable organization or person.
In person meetings / stakeholder engagement / data collection becomes impossible in some countries	Switch to virtual methods

The procedures for mitigating risks will depend on the nature and severity of the risks. The project will use the PM² Risk Assessment Thresholds Matrix (figure below). The risk level will be calculated by the product of likelihood and impact according to the matrix.

		Impact				
		1=Very low	2=Low	3=Medium	4=High	5=Very high
Likelihood	5=Very high	5	10	15	20	25
	4=High	4	8	12	16	20
	3=Medium	3	6	9	12	15
	2=Low	2	4	6	8	10
	1=Very low	1	2	3	4	5

Legend:

	Risks can be accepted, contingency plans may be developed.
	Risks cannot be accepted, a risk response strategy should be developed (avoid, reduce, transfer/ share)
	Unacceptable – immediate risk reduction or avoidance response
	Risk appetite

Generally, identified risks will be brought to the EB for discussion of resolution. The EB may be summoned by the coordinators earlier to tackle risks, if necessary. If no resolution is reached at the EB, the coordinators ask for the opinion of the EAB and/or convene the GA. In case of discrepancy on opinions on risk mitigation measures, the decision of the GA will be the prevailing course of action for risk mitigation.